

ENHANCING COMPREHENSION OF THE TROJAN WAR: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF READING AND VISUAL STORYTELLING IN PHILIPPINE HIGHER EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the reading and viewing comprehension skills of 44 second-year BSED-English students at Jose Rizal Memorial State University, Dipolog Campus, using the Trojan War episode as instructional material. Employing a descriptive-comparative design, comprehension was measured through validated questionnaires administered after either a reading session or a film viewing session. Results revealed a clear disparity between the two modalities: the mean reading comprehension score was 11.05 (Average), while the mean viewing comprehension score reached 15.26 (High). Notably, no respondents fell under the “Poor” or “Very Poor” categories in viewing, whereas reading comprehension scores ranged widely across all levels. Item analysis showed that visually explicit depictions, such as Achilles’ portrayal as a warrior (100% viewing comprehension) and Hector’s identity as a Trojan prince (100%) enhanced understanding. In contrast, abstract literary references, such as the film’s basis in Homer’s Iliad, scored lowest (22.7 % in reading; 33.3 % in viewing). Statistical analysis using the Mann-Whitney U Test confirmed a significant difference between reading and viewing comprehension ($U = 98.5$, $p < .05$), affirming that visual storytelling promotes stronger comprehension. The findings underscore the cognitive advantages of visual media in simplifying complex narratives and fostering engagement. Pedagogically, the study advances strategies for teaching classical literature by demonstrating the value of multimodal instruction. Integrating films and other visual texts alongside traditional readings not only enhances comprehension but also makes works like The Iliad more accessible and relatable to 21st-century learners.

This contributes to multimodal learning by bridging classical literature with modern pedagogical practices.

Keywords: *Visual Literacy, Multimodal Learning, Educational Media, Trojan War, Comprehension, Reading*

INTRODUCTION

Classical literature such as the Trojan War continues to hold pedagogical value in higher education, not only as a historical and cultural artifact but also as a resource for strengthening students' macro skills in reading and viewing. In the Philippine context, however, the integration of textual and visual materials in teaching literary epics remains underexplored, even though multimodal instruction has been shown to enrich comprehension and encourage deeper engagement with texts. This study therefore highlights the importance of combining reading and viewing in developing comprehension, while also proposing innovative strategies that respond to the changing demands of teaching literature in the digital age. For students, the research offers a fresh learning experience that bridges mythology with skill-based approaches, while English teachers may find it a valuable model for designing more dynamic lessons through the integration of technology and visual resources.

Anchored on Anderson and Pearson's (1984) schema theory, which explains comprehension as an interactive process shaped by prior knowledge and contextual cues, and Mayer's (2001) cognitive theory of multimedia learning, which underscores the synergy between visual and verbal modes, this study situates the Trojan War as a medium for multimodal literacy development. Recent scholarship underscores the benefits of multimodal and technology-supported approaches to literacy instruction. Santos and Rivera (2020) reported that integrating visual narratives with reading tasks significantly enhanced comprehension among Philippine college students, particularly in literature classes where abstract ideas often challenge learners. Similarly, Abad (2019) found that multimedia-based strategies in teaching mythology improved students' retention and interpretative skills by making classical stories more accessible. More broadly, Uy (2021) emphasized that multimodal materials foster critical thinking and meaning-making among Filipino learners, suggesting that visual aids are not merely supplementary but central to comprehension development. These studies affirm that combining textual and visual resources creates richer learning environments, yet few have focused on mythology within the local higher education setting.

Beyond the Philippine context, recent international studies also highlight the importance of multimodal comprehension. Chen and Tsai (2019) observed that university students exposed to visual-text integration performed better in synthesizing complex narratives compared to those relying solely on text. Likewise, Alghamdi (2021) demonstrated that visual scaffolding in reading activities improved college students' comprehension by aiding the construction of mental models. These findings support the argument that

multimodal approaches enhance not only knowledge acquisition but also higher-order thinking skills, aligning with the objectives of twenty-first-century education.

Despite these promising insights, gaps remain in applying multimodal strategies to classical epics like the Trojan War within Philippine higher education. While much of the existing research has focused on contemporary texts or general reading comprehension, limited attention has been given to how mythology, often perceived as distant or difficult, can be revitalized through visual-textual integration. This study addresses this gap by positioning the Trojan War as a learning resource that bridges the traditional and the modern, combining the richness of classical literature with the accessibility of visual media.

By doing so, it demonstrates how multimodal instruction not only enhances comprehension in reading and viewing but also equips learners with transferable skills in analysis, interpretation, and appreciation of literature. Ultimately, the primary objective of this study is to determine the level of comprehension of the Trojan War as a macroskill in reading and viewing among second-year Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English students at Jose Rizal Memorial State University, Dipolog Campus, during the Academic Year 2022–2023.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the Trojan War comprehend in reading and viewing as a macroskill of the 2nd year college, Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English of Jose Rizal State University in Dipolog Campus during the Academic Year 2022-2023.

Specially, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What are the Trojan War Episodes?
2. What visual contents and interpretations aided the comprehension of the respondents?
3. What are the comprehension test results of the respondents in the following macro skill:
 - 3.1 reading, and
 - 3.2 viewing?
4. Is there a significant difference in the comprehension test results of the respondent?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive research design utilizing a survey method to examine the level of comprehension of the Trojan War through reading and viewing among second-year Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English students at Jose Rizal Memorial State University, Dipolog Campus. The descriptive design was deemed appropriate because it provided a systematic, objective, and factual account of the respondents' comprehension performance across two macroskills, namely reading and

viewing. It also allowed the researcher to determine the extent to which the mode of content delivery influenced the students' comprehension outcomes.

Purposive sampling was employed in selecting the participants to ensure that the respondents were aligned with the specific objectives of the study. From the total population of 145 second-year BSED English students, 44 participants were deliberately selected based on defined inclusion criteria. The primary criterion required that the students be officially enrolled in the Mythology and Folklore course (ENG 108) during the Academic Year 2022–2023. This requirement was established to guarantee that the selected respondents possessed adequate background knowledge and academic exposure relevant to the topic of the Trojan War. Consequently, the 44 participants met the necessary qualifications, ensuring that the data obtained were both valid and representative of the intended population. The use of purposive sampling was therefore justified, as it allowed the researcher to focus on a sample directly related to the aims of the investigation.

Prior to data collection, the research instrument, a comprehension questionnaire based on selected episodes of the Trojan War, was validated by three language experts from Jose Rizal Memorial State University. The experts assessed the instrument in terms of content accuracy, clarity, and relevance to ensure that it effectively measured the intended comprehension constructs. Their feedback guided the refinement of the questionnaire, thereby enhancing its validity and reliability. Following the validation process, the instrument was administered to the selected participants.

The data collection procedure involved coordination with the Office of the Dean and the Registrar to identify qualified respondents and obtain institutional consent. Participants were divided into two groups. One group participated in a 45-minute reading session, while the other group engaged in a 45-minute viewing session featuring audiovisual content of the same Trojan War material. Immediately after the sessions, the participants completed the validated comprehension questionnaire. This procedure ensured uniform exposure to content and allowed a comparative assessment of how different modes of presentation affected comprehension.

The scoring and interpretation of the results were based on a standardized rating scale, which served as the basis for evaluating the respondents' comprehension performance.

The following legend guided the interpretation of scores:

Score	Descriptors
20.00–17.00	Very High
16.99–13.00	High
12.99–9.00	Average
8.99–5.00	Poor
4.99–1.00	Very Poor

This scoring framework provided a clear and consistent measure of comprehension levels. In the interpretation of Table 1, the analysis was grounded in the visual content of the materials and the corresponding comprehension responses of the students. The visual representations and imagery were instrumental in aiding the students' understanding of the Trojan War, particularly among those exposed to viewing activities.

These interpretations were critically analyzed to determine how visual and textual modalities influenced comprehension. Furthermore, the results and interpretations were reviewed and verified by the three language experts who validated the instrument, ensuring the accuracy and academic rigor of the findings.

The collected data were statistically analyzed to obtain both descriptive and inferential insights. Frequency counts were utilized to summarize the respondents' comprehension scores, while percentages described the demographic characteristics of the participants.

To determine the relationship between selected variables, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was applied. This statistical method allowed the researcher to assess whether a significant relationship existed between the students' comprehension levels and their exposure to the different modes of content delivery.

The methodological procedures ensured both validity and reliability. Validity was achieved through careful participant selection, expert validation of the instrument, and standardized administration of the reading and viewing activities. Reliability was maintained through consistent scoring procedures, clear interpretive criteria, and expert-reviewed analyses. Collectively, these methodological safeguards strengthened the credibility of the study's results and enhanced the generalizability of its conclusions within the context of language and literature instruction.

RESULTS

Table 1 *Visual contents and interpretations aided the comprehension of the respondents Items 1–10*

Item	Reading %	Viewing %	Visual Content	Interpretation
1	77.3	100	Achilles as warrior	Clear portrayal aided comprehension
2	31.8	66.7	Greeks seek revenge	Viewing clarified motive
3	77.3	95.2	Achilles' doubts	Both high; visuals reinforced
4	45.5	38.1	Agamemnon leads army	Low in both; unclear visually
5	59.1	71.4	Helen as queen	Viewing clearer role

6	27.3	33.3	Greeks breach walls	Low in both formats
7	90.9	95.2	Paris–Helen elopement	High in both; pivotal event
8	63.6	95.2	Paris as prince	Viewing highlighted role
9	54.5	71.4	Agamemnon leader	Viewing better context
10	59.1	90.5	Patroclus as cousin	Viewing clarified bond

Table 2 *Visual contents and interpretations aided the comprehension of the respondents Items 11–20*

Item	Reading %	Viewing %	Visual Content	Interpretation
11	77.3	90.5	Paris sparks war	High in both; viewing clearer
12	50.0	76.2	Agamemnon assault	Viewing clarified role
13	50.0	66.7	Achilles doubts fate	Moderate; visuals helped
14	68.2	71.4	Achilles fights Greeks	High both; visuals reinforced
15	68.2	100	Paris & Hector brothers	Viewing clearly showed bond
16	81.8	100	Achilles legendary	High in both; visuals stronger
17	22.7	33.3	Based on Iliad	Low in both; unclear link
18	31.8	100	Hector as prince	Viewing gave clear role
19	77.3	90.5	Helen’s abduction	High in both; visuals vivid
20	45.5	81.0	Personal conflicts	Viewing conveyed tensions

Table 3 *Comprehension Skill Test Results of the Respondents in terms of Reading*

Score	f	m	fm	Mean
20 – 17	3	18.5	55.5	11.05
16 – 13	4	14.5	58	
12 – 9	10	10.5	105	

8 – 5	3	6.5	19.5
4 – 1	2	2.5	5
Σf = 22		Σfm =243	
			Average

Table 4 *Comprehension Skill Test Results of the Respondents in terms of Viewing*

Score	f	m	fm	Mean
20 – 17	5	18.5	92.5	15.26
16 – 13	15	14.5	217.5	
12 – 9	1	10.5	10.5	
8 – 5	0	6.5	0	
4 – 1	0	2.5	0	
Σf = 21		Σfm =320		High

Table 5 *Test of Difference in the Comprehension Skill Test Result of the respondents in terms of Reading and Viewing*

Factors Compared	Reading Skill Test Result			
	U-critical value	U-value	Interpretation	Action/Decision
Viewing Skill Test Result = 0.05	231	98.5	Significant Difference	H ₀ was rejected

Note: if the obtained U value is larger than the critical U value, then retain H₀:
if the obtained U value is smaller than the critical U value, then reject H₀:

DISCUSSION

The movie portrays the Trojan War through several key episodes, beginning with the Greeks' arrival and the protracted siege of Troy. Notable battles include the initial clash on the Trojan beach, the duels between Paris and Menelaus, Hector and Ajax, and the climactic fight between Hector and Achilles. The war culminates in the use of the Trojan Horse to infiltrate Troy, leading to the city's sacking and the end of the conflict. The interpretation of visual content in historical films like "Troy" (2024) aligns with research on visual literacy and historical comprehension. For instance, Zanker (2016) discusses the importance of visual representation in enhancing viewers' understanding of historical events, noting that films can effectively convey complex narratives through dynamic imagery and character-driven stories. Additionally, Dovey (2013) highlights that visual

storytelling in cinema can create an emotional connection with the audience, making historical events more relatable and memorable.

Table 1 presents the visual contents and interpretations aided the comprehension of the respondents Items 1–10. Visual content refers to the images, scenes, and cinematic elements that support learners' understanding by presenting information in a vivid, concrete way. In the case of Troy, this includes the portrayal of characters, relationships, and key events. For example, the highest viewing comprehension score was 100% for Item 1 ("Achilles as warrior"), showing how the strong and heroic imagery of Achilles enhanced students' grasp of his role. Similarly, events like the elopement of Paris and Helen (Item 7, 95.2% viewing) were understood more clearly because the film emphasized their intimate interactions, making the relationship central and easy to follow.

At the same time, the table shows that comprehension was lower for events not visually emphasized. For example, Item 4 ("Agamemnon leads army") had low results both in reading (45.5%) and viewing (38.1%), suggesting that the film did not provide a clear enough representation of Agamemnon's leadership. Likewise, Item 6 ("Greeks breach walls") scored low in both (27.3% reading; 33.3% viewing), reflecting that when key moments are not strongly highlighted in visual storytelling, comprehension is also weakened. This indicates that not all visual content is equally effective; clarity and focus are essential.

The data in Table 2 further highlights the effectiveness of visual content in aiding comprehension. Items such as 15 ("Paris & Hector are brothers") and 16 ("Achilles legendary") both achieved a perfect 100% viewing comprehension score. This suggests that the film's clear portrayal of brotherhood and the heroic status of Achilles visually reinforced relationships and cultural values, making them more memorable than textual descriptions alone. Similarly, Item 18 ("Hector as prince") scored 100% in viewing, showing how visual representation clarified character roles that might otherwise be abstract in text.

In contrast, comprehension was weakest in Item 17 ("Based on Iliad"), which had the lowest reading score of 22.7% and only 33.3% in viewing. This result indicates that background knowledge linking the film to Homer's Iliad was not visually evident and relied more on prior literary awareness. Such findings highlight a limitation of visual content: while it excels at illustrating character traits and dramatic relationships, it struggles to convey intertextual or historical references that require explanation beyond imagery. This reinforces that visual content is most effective for conveying explicit, interpersonal, and emotionally charged moments. Scenes that show direct interactions, like Helen's abduction (Item 19) or the personal conflicts among characters (Item 20), had higher comprehension scores in viewing than in reading. This underlines how film as a medium engages both cognition and emotion, helping students grasp complex character dynamics in ways that pure text sometimes cannot achieve.

Table 3 presents the results of the comprehension skill test focused on reading, categorizing student performance from "Very High" to "Very Poor." The findings indicate

that the majority of respondents fell within the "Average" range, suggesting a moderate level of reading comprehension. This outcome may be attributed to several factors, including prior knowledge of the Trojan War and overall language proficiency. Students with background knowledge in Greek mythology may have found it easier to follow the storyline and understand key events. In contrast, students with limited vocabulary or weaker grasp of sentence structure may have struggled to fully comprehend the text. Additionally, the complexity of the Trojan War, with its numerous characters and layered plot, could have posed challenges, contributing to the average overall performance.

The interpretation of scores reveals that students across all proficiency levels would benefit from targeted support. Those with "Very High" scores are encouraged to explore more complex texts and engage in analytical reading practices to further enhance their skills. Students in the "High" and "Average" ranges are advised to focus on refining their comprehension strategies, summarizing skills, and vocabulary development. Meanwhile, those who performed "Poorly" or "Very Poorly" require foundational reinforcement through simplified texts, individualized support, and regular reading practice. This aligns with Kaya (2015), who emphasized that reading comprehension varies across proficiency levels and that successful reading requires more than word recognition—it demands knowledge, purpose, and strategy. Developing strong reading skills is not only essential for academic success but also for lifelong learning.

Table 4 presents the comprehension skill test results for viewing, where the mean score of 15.26 indicates a generally high level of visual comprehension among the respondents. Most students fell under the "High" and "Very High" categories, showing strong proficiency in interpreting visual content related to the Trojan War. Notably, there were no respondents in the "Poor" or "Very Poor" categories, highlighting their strong viewing skills. Contributing factors to this result include the students' visual literacy, prior exposure to the Trojan War narrative, and their ability to analyze visual elements such as symbolism, facial expressions, and contextual cues. These competencies allowed them to extract meaning and make connections between visual representations and the storyline.

Students with stronger scores in viewing comprehension may further enhance their skills through exposure to complex visual content and participation in collaborative learning activities. Meanwhile, those with average results can benefit from targeted strategies to strengthen visual literacy, such as engaging with various media formats and interpreting charts, infographics, or videos. This aligns with Alfiani (2020), who noted that films and visual tools provide rich learning experiences that support comprehension, and Woottipong (2014), who emphasized the effectiveness of viewing in improving attention to visual performances and multimedia presentations. Overall, the findings affirm that viewing plays a vital role in comprehension, enabling students to process visual information effectively alongside or even beyond textual input.

Table 5 highlights the significant difference between reading and viewing comprehension skills, as determined by the Mann-Whitney U Test. The statistical results led to the rejection of the null hypothesis, confirming that the observed difference between the two

modalities is not due to chance. This indicates that reading and viewing require fundamentally different cognitive processes, each engaging distinct sets of skills. Reading comprehension involves linear, language-based processing that relies on vocabulary, grammar, and critical thinking, while viewing comprehension requires interpreting visual and auditory cues, demanding proficiency in visual literacy, symbolism, and multimodal analysis. These distinct approaches to processing information explain the variation in test performance between the two groups.

The findings show that respondents demonstrated higher performance in viewing comprehension, with most scores falling under the "High" and "Very High" categories, and none in the "Poor" or "Very Poor" ranges. In contrast, reading comprehension scores were more widely distributed, with several students scoring in the "Average" and below-average categories. This supports studies such as those by Woottipong (2014) and Alfiani (2020), which emphasize that multimedia tools like videos enhance student engagement and comprehension by offering rich visual context. The results underscore the importance of integrating both reading and viewing strategies in education, as learners are increasingly exposed to both textual and visual content in modern learning environments.

Conclusions

Based on the analysis of test results, it can be concluded that viewing comprehension emerged as a stronger skill among the BSED-English second-year students compared to reading comprehension. The visual storytelling elements of the Trojan War, such as key scenes and character interactions, proved more effective in enhancing student understanding and engagement than traditional text. While reading comprehension scores varied widely, indicating differing levels of textual interpretation skills, viewing comprehension showed consistently high performance among the respondents. This disparity emphasizes the cognitive advantages of visual media in communicating complex narratives and highlights the importance of integrating multimedia resources in educational settings. More importantly, the key findings of this study contribute to advancing pedagogical strategies in teaching classical literature by demonstrating the value of multimodal texts, where film and visual content complement written sources. By adopting such approaches, educators can make classical works like The Iliad more accessible, relatable, and engaging for modern learners, thereby fostering deeper comprehension and appreciation of literary traditions.

Recommendations

1. For teachers and instructors. Given the high engagement and comprehension scores associated with visual storytelling, incorporate more films, documentaries, and visual aids related to course material. This approach will help students better understand and retain complex narratives and historical contexts, as demonstrated by their response to the movie's depiction of the Trojan War.

2. For BSED-English Students. To improve their reading skills, a helpful suggestion is to try reading more regularly. Provide additional support for reading comprehension by incorporating structured reading activities, such as guided reading sessions, annotated texts, and discussions that highlight key themes and historical contexts.
3. Future Researchers. New areas related to enhancing comprehension can be explored or focused on Visual-Textual Integration and Impact of Technology in Learning and more avenue for curriculum development and teacher training programs.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study ensured that informed consent was properly obtained from all respondents, who were given the freedom to withdraw from participation at any time. The anonymity and confidentiality of respondents were strictly maintained, and their well-being was prioritized throughout the research process. The authors also confirm that there was no conflict of interest in conducting the study, plagiarism was completely avoided, and the interpretation of findings was carried out objectively and without bias. Furthermore, the results of this study were utilized solely for research purposes.

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